

The role of videographic hydrometry for Digital Twins of sewer systems

Robert Ljubičić¹, Damjan Ivetić², Miloš Milašinović³

^{1,2,3} Digital Water Engineering Lab, Faculty of Civil Engineering, University of Belgrade, Serbia

email: rljubicic@grf.bg.ac.rs

email: divetice@grf.bg.ac.rs

email: mmilasinnovic@grf.bg.ac.rs

ABSTRACT

The integration of Digital Twins into drainage management systems offers unprecedented opportunities for real-time monitoring, predictive modeling, and adaptive control of urban water infrastructure. One of the main challenges, especially in countries with underdeveloped infrastructure monitoring, lies in acquiring accurate (near) real-time data with high temporal resolution to capture flow dynamics across diverse hydraulic conditions. Videographic (camera-based) measurement techniques offer an opportunity to fill such gaps, as they provide non-intrusive, scalable, and visually verifiable data to be used in conjunction with traditional, but often very costly, monitoring approaches. While videographic measurement techniques have been successfully deployed in riverine systems in the past, their introduction to closed-conduit municipal systems has been lagging.

The DIGIDRAIN project aims to create a framework for setting up Digital Twins for urban sewage systems. This effort is also to include the application of custom-made low-cost camera-based solutions in key network locations, and investigate the opportunities and challenges which they provide – (1) the choice of best-fitting image-processing methods depending on flow and ambient conditions, (2) cost effectiveness, (3) hardware reliability, and (4) the usefulness and uncertainty of such data for the creation, calibration, and exploitation of the resulting Digital Twin.

Preliminary results from a real-world test of a low-cost camera-based setup are presented. The tests are performed in harsh low-light winter conditions with a device installed for autonomous operation inside a maintenance hole. While the acquired data is analysed and provides good agreement with reference measurements, several key challenges – persistent power supply, low-light visibility, visibility issues due to aerosol dispersion, etc. – have been identified with adequate mitigation strategies considered for future work.

1. Methodology

The testing was performed in a sewer manhole, just upstream of the nearby recipient. Choice of the testing site was made based on the presence of a cascade inside the manhole, which provided unsubmerged inflow conditions in the incoming pipe and a univocal discharge-stage relationship. Based on the known pipe diameter, the outflow depth could be determined exclusively from video information, without the need for an external depth sensor. Reference measurements were performed at the upstream end of the incoming pipe using a bed-mounted electromagnetic flow meter (Ivetić et al. 2018, 2019).

A custom low-cost camera setup was created using off-the-shelf components, as shown in Fig. 1a, with a lightweight plastic casing shown in Fig. 1b. The system was based on the Raspberry Pi system-on-a-chip platform, with a dedicated power management board to provide deep-sleep and timed wakeup capabilities, prolonging the device's autonomy. The camera was equipped with two infrared LEDs for low-light recording conditions. Total equipment cost was approx. 150 USD.

Five-second-long videos were obtained at 10-minute intervals, which were processed using optical flow method using free SSIMS-Flow software (Ljubičić et al. 2024). Adequate preprocessing pipeline was obtained based on a sample video and was the same for all videos, enabling automated analysis of all obtained videos.

Fig. 1. Hardware: a) measuring device schematic, b) device casing.

2. Results and conclusions

As measurements were performed at external temperatures close to or below 0°C , severe temperature gradients, along with the dispersion of aerosols caused occasional fogging of the camera lens. A dedicated automated contrast-based filtering technique was developed to identify and interpolate low-quality footage. Postprocessed data showed remarkable agreement with the reference data over a majority of the test period (Fig. 2), falling well within the 95% confidence interval, with the exception of the data between 9am on the 28th and 13pm on the 29th of December due to the formation of a temporary physical blockage at the very end of the inflow pipe. Upon the removal of the blockage, the results returned to the previous level of accuracy.

The field experience highlighted several key conclusions related to the future role of videographic measurements in sewage systems, with main being that hardware and site conditions play a far more critical role than software algorithms and processing methods. In the current state-of-the-art, camera-based measurements can be a great supplement to traditional measurement methods in key locations with adequate ambient conditions, particularly as a valuable control mechanism. However, the possibilities of visual verification, reusability of image data with emerging processing techniques, software, and AI tools, make for strong advocates for the continuous development and deployment of affordable camera-based devices which can aid the development and reliability of Digital Twins.

Fig. 2. Discharge comparison over time: calibrated rating curve in the upstream manhole (full line) incl. 95% confidence limits (dotted lines) and camera (markers).

Acknowledgements

This research has been supported by the DIGIDRAIN project (funding from the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, research program DIASPORA 2023: joint research, under grant agreement number: 17823 – City-scale digital twins for urban drainage systems: bringing “smart” to water infrastructure).

References

- Ivetić D., Prodanović D. and Stojadinović L. (2018). Bed-mounted Electro Magnetic meters: Implications for robust velocity measurement in Urban Drainage Systems. *Journal of Hydrology*, 566, 455-469.
- Ivetić D., Prodanović D., Stojadinović L. and Pavlović D. (2019). Bed-mounted electromagnetic meters: Assessment of the (missing) technical parameters. *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, 68, 101588.
- Ljubičić R., Dal Sasso S. F. and Zindović B. (2024) SSIMS-Flow: Image Velocimetry Workbench for Open-Channel Flow Rate Estimation. *Environmental Modeling & Software*, 173, 105938.